

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

The impact of alcohol consumption on employee job performance

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Abstract

Background: Most people know that job performance generally refers to how well an employee is accomplishing his or her tasks and achieve the target, but there are number of factors that determine the level and quality of employee job performance.

Objective: The purpose of this study was to examine the impact of Alcohol consumption on the self-reported work performance among the people of Jalalabad, Kyrgystan.

Materials and Methods: A descriptive cross-sectional study was done through online Google forms for a period of 3 months from September to November 2023 among 160 local people. Various dimensions of work performance are compared across different levels of alcohol consumption in the study.

Result: In this study the respondents age range was 20-40 years with mean age of 30 ± 1 years. Out of 160 respondents, male predominance was found over females with 68.1%. The largest percentage 67.5% of them consume alcohol due the stress they have in their Job. Most respondents 67.5% were found to have no family history of drinking alcohol. Regarding the impact of their job performance, only 23.9%(n=28) respondents experiences a significant impact on their job performance.

Conclusion: Our study into the impact of alcohol drinking among Jalalabad residents revealed a concerning prevalence of 73% of the 160 respondents. This emphasizes the importance of targeted interventions, community education, and support networks in addressing alcohol's influence on the local population's well-being. Understanding and tackling the underlying causes of alcohol misuse in Jalalabad will be critical to building a better and more resilient community.

Keywords: Alcohol; Consumption; Job Performance; Ethical; Statistical

1. Introduction

Effect of alcohol consumption might occur quickly. Drinking excessively can have a number of negative outcomes and increase your risk of developing a variety of diseases. Globally, among the population aged 25-59 years, the core of the working age population determined alcohol to be the highest risk factor for mortality and disability. (1). The WHO estimates that hazardous alcohol use causes around 3 million deaths globally each year (2). Alcohol can impair focus and coordination in an employee's work performance. Excessive alcohol intake is a substantial risk factor for disease, disability, and mortality, and has been linked to over 200 diseases and injuries.(3) Older persons struggle more than younger people with their job performance. According to the 2023 poll, Zimbabwe ranks first in alcohol consumption, with 62.8 liters per capita (4).The World Health Organization (WHO) defines a drug as any chemical compound that,

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when ingested, can alter one or more of the body's processes. Alcohol, a legalized narcotic, is one of the most often abused substances in the world. The World Drug Report (2013) recognizes alcohol consumption as a global concern with major consequences for people's health, security, socioeconomic standing, and cultural welfare (5). Alcohol intake can affect activity performance in a range of settings, including the workplace. Frone's integrative model of employee substance use and productivity suggests that off-the-job drinking leads to absenteeism and tardiness, while on-the-job drinking leads to early departure and poor performance (6). Alcohol intake has been linked to an increased risk of illness, disability, and death (7). People who were content with their working environment and working hours were more likely to routinely drink (8), as alcohol is one of the most affordable forms of addiction; this explains why alcoholism is so prevalent (9). Hierarchical multiple regression analyses indicated that gender, friends alcohol consumption, coping, and social motives for drinking were significant predictors of study participants alcohol consumption (10).

2. Material and Methods

It was a cross-sectional study among 160 respondents, which was done online through Google forms from September to November 2023 in Jalalabad, Kyrgyzstan. Out of 160 respondents were selected from one areas through convenient sampling technique from where only 117 were included in the study group. Of the 160 surveyed participants only 117 reported having tried and consumed alcohol in their lifetime. Data were collected through specifically developed structured questionnaire, which was developed based on the literature review. The questionnaire had four sections. First section was dealing with socio-demographic information of respondents. The second section was regarding the knowledge on alcohol consumption, third section was on habit they have regarding alcohol consumption. In fourth section, there were questions related to the impact on their job performance.

3. Results

A total of 160 respondent from different working area of Jalalabad were selected from the sampling size where as the age range was 20-40 years with mean age of 30 ± 1 years. Out of 160 respondents, male predominance was found over females with 68.1%. Similarly out of 160 respondents 43 respondents they have never consumed alcohol so they were not included in the study.

Table 1 Socio Demographic Information of the respondents

S.No	Variables	Frequency(f) N=160	Percentage (%)
1	RELIGION		
	Muslim	104	65.0
	Christian	50	31.3
	Other	6	3.8
2	MARITAL STATUS		
	Married	111	69.4
	Unmarried	44	27.5
	Prefer not say	5	3.1
3	OCCUPATION		
	Private Job holder	111	69.4
	Gov Job Holder	34	21.3
	Small Business	9	5.6
	Retired	6	3.8
4	Nationality		
	Kyrgyzstan	155	96.9
	Uzbekistan	5	3.1

It shows the distribution of respondents according to their socio-demographic information where it shows that majority of respondents 65% are Muslims. Almost 69.4% respondents reported to be married. Majority of respondents are engaged in Private Job whereas 3.8 % indicated that they were retired. Where 97% respondents were from Kyrgyzstan and remaining 3.1% were from Uzbekistan. (Table 1)

Figure 1 Distribution on the basis of whether they have tried any type of alcoholic beverage or not?

In the study it shows out of 160 respondents (117)73.20% of respondents have consumed alcohol in some form while the remaining 26.80% have abstained from trying it.

Figure 2 Distribution of respondents according to their drinking habit

Above figure shows that: 46.2% of the respondents reported drinking alcohol on a monthly or less, 36.8% of respondents indicated drinking alcohol 2 to 4 times a month, 13.7% of the respondents reported drinking alcohol 2 to 3 times a week whereas 3.4% stated drinking alcohol 4 or more times a week. This provides insight into the frequency of alcohol consumption among surveyed individuals.

Table 2 Distribution of respondents according to the reason of their drinking habit

SN	Responses	Frequency	Percentage
1	Relaxation	28	23.9
2	Job Stress	79	67.5
3	Social Reason	10	8.5
4	Total	117	100.0

Above table shows that majority 67.5% of the respondents consume alcohol due to Job stress followed by 23.9 % respondents consume for relaxation and remaining 8.5% started to consume due to social gathering.

Table 3 Distribution of respondents according to their preferred timing for drinking

SN	Responses	Frequency	Percentage
1	Any Day	19	16.2
2	Week Days	21	17.9
3	Week end only	77	65.8
4	Total	117	100.0

Above table shows that the respondents prefer to drink alcohol during weekends only that is 65.8% whereas 16.2% consume any day which means they don't have any specific day for them to drink.

Figure 3 Distribution of respondents according to the family history of alcohol

Above figure shows that out of 117 respondents 30.8% respondents had family history of drinking alcohol whereas a majority of 67.5% respondents were found to have a no family history of drinking alcohol.

Table 4 Distribution of respondent according to their willingness to quit drinking habit

SN	Responses	Frequency	Percentage
1	Yes	46	39.3
2	No	71	60.6
	Total	117	100.0

Of 117 participants, 39.3% attempted to quit their drinking habit while the remaining 60.6% did not make any attempt to quit. (Table 4)

Table 5 Distribution of respondents according to the impact on thier job performance

SN	Options	Frequency	Percentage
1	Highly Impact	28	23.9
2	Lesser Impact	89	76.1
	Total	117	100.0

Above table shows that only 23.9%(n=28) respondents experiences a significant impact on thier job performance meanwhile, the remaining 76.1% reported a lesser impact on their job performance.

Table 6 Distribution of respondents according to their job effect after having alcohol

SN	Responses	Frequency (n=117)	Percentage(%)	P-value
1	Concentrate on work			*0.038
	Yes	22	18.80%	
	No	95	81.19%	
2	Taken leave or absent at work			
	Yes	27	23.1	
	No	90	76.9	
3	Have you ever been hospitalized			
	Yes	15	12.8	
	No	102	87.2	
4	Traffic accident			*0.043
	Yes	74	63.2	
	No	43	36.8	
5	Irritated with colleague			*0.025
	Yes	86	73.5	
	No	31	26.5	
6	Warning from Manager			
	Yes	49	41.9	
	No	68	58.1	
7	Completed task on time			
	Yes	50	42.7	
	No	67	57.3	

*Statistically Significant

Regarding affect in job after having alcohol lack of concentration was found to be statistically significant correlation with p-value 0.038. Similarly different form of accident and getting irritated with working colleague at work environment with p-value 0.043 and p-value 0.025 respectively were also found to statistically significant. Remaing effects like taking leave or being absent at work due to drinking alcohol, getting warning from manager, not completing task on time were not found significant.

4. Discussion

It is critical to understand that, while moderate alcohol intake may not constitute a substantial risk to many people, excessive or reckless drinking can result in health problems, addiction, and societal implications. Many people drink in social contexts to connect with others and improve social relationships. Some civilizations use alcohol into their rituals, celebrations, and religious activities. Some people drink alcohol to deal with stress or to unwind after a long day. To highlight the same issue, this study evaluated the practices of alcohol drinking and its impact on job performance among local residents of middle age in Jalalabad.

A total of 160 respondents from various working areas in Jalal-abad were chosen from the sampling size, with the majority 73.1% (117) classified as having a drinking habit, while 43 respondents had never taken alcohol and were thus removed from further study. In addition, males outnumbered females by 68.1%. Historically, there has been a cultural

misconception that males consume more alcohol. Social standards, cultural influences, and individual actions all have an impact on alcohol consumption trends across genders.

In this study, respondents were asked about their family history of alcohol consumption, which revealed that 30.8% of the 117 respondents had a family history of alcohol consumption, while the majority, 67.5%, had no family history of drinking. This finding does not indicate a probable family influence on alcohol use. A comparable study conducted in Ciudad de Carmen Campeche, Mexico, discovered that 57.6% of adolescents reported that persons living with them use alcoholic beverages (11).

According to the findings of this study, 69.4% of respondents worked in the private sector, while 21.3% worked for the government. Similarly, a study conducted in the United Kingdom examined people's experiences in both the public and private sectors. People working in the private sector were 38% more likely than government employees to report drinking alcohol at work (12).

In our study, 63.2% of respondents were involved in an RTA or traffic collision and tested positive for alcohol usage. According to earlier studies conducted by the University of Athens, Greece (2011-2017), alcohol use was responsible for 40.7% of RTA deaths (13).

This study discovered that 23.1% of respondents who consume alcohol may be missing from the workforce, but Mezuk's study on Job Stress and Depressive Symptoms stated that workers who drink excessively may be away from the workplace. (14)

Our study has shown statistically significant correlation between alcohol consumption and decreased concentration. As because alcohol affects the central nervous system, leading to impairments in cognitive function, including attention, memory and concentration. Similarly different form of accident and getting irritated with working colleague at work environment with p-value 0.043 and p-value 0.025 respectively were also found to statistically significant. Alcohol can affect mood regulation and exacerbate feeling of irritability which may lead to conflicts with coworkers. Additionally alcohol use can impair judgement and decision making as well as potentially influencing interpersonal interactions at working place.

5. Conclusion

This study's findings show a considerable prevalence of alcohol consumption among Jalalabad locals, with 117 out of 160 claiming to be affected. The implications extend beyond personal health, with known consequences for job performance and an increased risk of traffic accidents. Many workers reported difficulty concentrating at work, which can affect productivity and job satisfaction. Furthermore, alcohol-related irritability among coworkers worsens workplace dynamics, potentially leading to strained relationships and low morale.

Limitations

Because the number of participants were relatively small and restricted to urban areas, the prevalence of alcoholism may not accurately represent the jalalabad region. The study of the association between job performance and drinking has been very restricted in academic studies. As a result, there may be gaps in our understanding of the potential relationship between job performance and alcoholism, emphasizing the need for additional study to explicate these dynamics and their implications for individuals, businesses, and public health.

Recommendation

By implementing complete solutions that include education, legislation, and support services, Jalalabad could reduce these negative outcomes and create a healthier and more enjoyable work environment for its inhabitants.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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